

A REPORT ON THE GEOLOGICAL FIELD MAPPING
OF SHARE, LAFIAGI AND SHONGA KWARA
STATE, NIGERIA.

SUBMITTED BY: **KEHINDE O. ALAMU**

(20D/57GM/00561)

GROUP TWO (2)

DEPARTMENT OF GEOLOGY AND MINERAL
SCIENCES,

FACULTY OF PURE & APPLIED SCIENCES,

KWARA STATE UNIVERSITY,

MALETE, NIGERIA.

CARRIED OUT FROM 21st-24th JUNE 2021

UNDER THE SUPERVISION OF

**DR. JIMOH Y.A, DR. UMAR I., MRS AMINU B. S.,
MRS SHAKIRAT M. A.**

TABLE OF CONTENT

Abstract

Acknowledge

Chapter one (General introduction)

1.1 General statement

1.2 Aim and Objectives

1.3 Scope of the study area

1.4 Physiography setting

Chapter two (Literature review)

2.1 Geology of Nigeria

2.2 Geology of the study area

2.2.1 Geology of Share

2.2.2 Geology of Shonga

2.2.3 Geology of Lafiagi

Chapter three

Field instrument and their uses

3.1 Hammer

Chisel

Clinometer compass

Field note

Reflective jacket

Topographical map

Paper tape

Field boot

Geographical Positioning System

Mapping board

Measuring tape

Digital camera

Tracing paper

Chapter four

Field trip in detail

Chapter five

5.1 Summary & Conclusions

5.2 Recommendation

ABSTRACT

Kwara state is located approximately between latitude $N8^{\circ}10'$ and $N9^{\circ}50'$, longitude $E3^{\circ}10'$ and $E6^{\circ}5'$. Share is situated in Ifelodun, Kwara, Nigeria, its geographical coordinates are latitudes of $N 8^{\circ} 49' 0''$ and longitudes $4^{\circ} 59' 0''$ E. The area is bordered by Lafiagi-share road and Tsaragi. Shonga is situated in Edu, Kwara, Nigeria, its geographical coordinates are longitude $9^{\circ} 1' 0''$ N, and latitude $5^{\circ} 9' 0''$ E. Lafiagi town, Kwara state is situated on the south bank of the Niger River, its geographical coordinates are longitude $8^{\circ} 51' 10.8''$, and latitude $5^{\circ} 24' 59.1''$. This area falls in North-Eastern part of Kwara state, and falls under North-Central Nigeria, which was produced by the Federal Survey of Nigeria in 1964. A five day field mapping exercise was carried out in this terrain with the goal of producing a geological map of the area showing spatial distribution of rock units. The locality is majorly dominated with the basement complex of the area (igneous and metamorphic) and also sedimentary basin (metamorphic and sedimentary).

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

I want to use this opportunity to thank God for making this session's field trip a reality. I also want to thank my parents for their unique love and support. Also I would love to give my thanks to Dr. Jimoh, Dr. Umar, Mrs Mariam and Mrs Shakirah for their guidance and tutorship they offered me and my colleagues during the field trip.

I will like to give thanks to my colleagues for their cooperation and making the field trip a very interesting and memorable one. Big thanks to you all.

CHAPTER ONE

1.1 INTRODUCTION

This report summarizes a geological mapping exercise initiated by the department of geology and mineral sciences, Kwara state University. The mapping exercise was completed in MAY 2023 and this report covers the North-Eastern quadrant of Kwara state, Nigeria. The trip covered a period of five days and this was carry-out in Share, Ifelodun Local Government, Kwara State.

The bulk work was done by field mapping of various exposures and outcrops encountered in all locations. Samples were taken from various exposures with the use of hammers and chisel to chip out hand-sized pieces from the whole rock masses. Measurements of numerous intrusions, trends of joint, trends of lineation, veins and some essential structural elements were done with the clinometer compass and distances were calculated with measuring tape, pace lengths and scaling distance from map.

After a period of approximately three days, we were able to give a general description of the lithological distribution of various rock types and delineate structures in the mapped area.

Also traversing was done with the aid of Global Positioning System (GPS) devices and clinometers compasses. The topographical map of the area gave us an insight of regional topography.

1.2 AIMS AND OBJECTIVES:

The main objective of this field mapping is to produce a geological map of the locality showing the rock lithology and the distribution of the rocks.

The objectives of the study includes;

- To enhance students understanding of geological field mapping and the geological history of the area.
- To enhance the ability of students to map a locality individually with the use of certain geologic tools whether or not they are conversant with the area.
- To give a better understanding of the geology of the study area.
- To identify economic importance attached to the mapped area
- Create avenue for students to have dependable experience in geological field mapping.
- Update and produce a geological map of the area

1.3

SCOPE OF THE STUDY AREA

SHARE

Share is situated in Ifelodun, Kwara, Nigeria, its geographical coordinates are latitudes of N $8^{\circ} 49' 0''$ and longitudes $4^{\circ} 59' 0''$ E. The area is bordered by lafiagi-share road and Tsaragi.

Fig 1: The map of Share as shown on the google map

SHONGA

Shonga is situated in Edu, Kwara, Nigeria, its geographical coordinates are longitude $9^{\circ} 1' 0''$ N, and latitude $5^{\circ} 9' 0''$ E

Fig. 2: Map data © 2023 showing Shonga

LAFIAGI

Lafiagi town, Kwara state is situated on the south bank of the Niger River, its geographical coordinates are longitude $8^{\circ}51'10.8''$ and latitude $5^{\circ}24'59.1''$.

Fig.3: Free Physical Map of Lafiagi

1.4

PHYSIOGRAPHY SETTING

Some of the outcrops and exposures are easily accessible because most of them are not too far from each other, while some of them have ridge exposures, road cut, river or stream cut etc. with the aid of the topographical map, the geographical positioning system, we were able to reach several locations and return safely. Access to the most remote outcrops location was gained by walking and also use of a motorcycles and vehicles were used.

GEOMORPHOLOGY

Geomorphology refers to the structure, origin, and development of the topographical features of the Earth surface. The geomorphologic features found in the area include mountains, dense and sparse vegetation and farmlands.

RELIEF AND TOPOGRAPHY

The mapped area consists of high and low lands terrain, massive and low lying outcrops. The topography of the area is also composed of minor roads, rivers, with dense and sparse vegetation (tall trees and grasses). It is dominantly medium to high relief and also presence of low reliefs as well.

CLIMATE

Climate can be defined as a long term prevalent weather conditions of an area, determined by Latitude, position relative to Oceans or continents and altitudes. There are two main climatic conditions in Kwara, namely:

- Rainy Season
- Dry Season

The climatic condition of our locations is tropical which is characterized with abundance of tall grasses dotted by few giant trees, except for the river channels which support rain-forest vegetation characterized by deciduous trees.

The rainy season have a good deal of rainfall with average annual rainfall of 1281mm and temperature to be 24.7⁰c while during the dry season, there is little or no rainfall with average annual temperature of 33.44⁰c in a year.

HUMAN ACTIVITIES

Most of the people of Share, Lafiagi and Shonga practice subsistence farming and petty trading to make their living. The food crops produced abundantly are maize, yam, cassava etc. They also engaged in commercial farming i.e. dealing in cash crop production e.g. cashew nut etc. They also engage in the productio

n of garri from cassava peels.

CHAPTER TWO

GEOLOGY OF NIGERIA

The **geology of Nigeria** formed beginning in the Archean and Proterozoic eons of the Precambrian. The country forms the Nigerian Province and more than half of its surface is igneous and metamorphic crystalline basement rock from the Precambrian. Between 2.9 billion and 500 million years ago, Nigeria was affected by three major orogeny mountain-building events and related igneous intrusions. Following the Pan-African orogeny, in the Cambrian at the time that multi-cellular life proliferated, Nigeria began to experience regional sedimentation and witnessed new igneous intrusions. By the Cretaceous period of the late Mesozoic, massive sedimentation was underway in different basins, due to a large marine transgression. By the Eocene, in the Cenozoic, the region returned to terrestrial conditions.

Nigeria has tremendous oil and natural gas resources housed in its thick sedimentary basins, as well as reserves of gold, lead, zinc, tantalite, columbite, coal and tin.

Stratigraphy, Tectonics & Geologic History

The oldest Precambrian rocks in Nigeria likely formed during the Archean or the Paleoproterozoic, forming the Benin gneiss, in the Benin-Nigeria Orogeny, formed during the Proterozoic Pan-African orogeny. The crystalline basement rock of the country is grouped as the Nigerian Province, a southern continuation of the central Hoggar reactivated basement.

The ancient rocks of the Nigerian Province are split up by thrust and shear zones. The Migmatite-Gneiss Complex covers half of Nigeria's surface area and encompasses Archean gray gneisses, with tonalite and granodiorite consistencies. Within this complex are occurrences of schist, migmatite, garnet, sillimanite, kyanite and staurolite, which together indicate high-grade metamorphism up to the level of amphibolite on the sequence of metamorphic facies. Granites are associated with charnockite bodies and granulite facies metamorphism.

The Migmatite-Gneiss Complex differs in the Ibadan area, in the southwest. Banded gneiss, schist and quartzite formed from the metamorphism of greywacke, shale and interbedded sandstones. Some amphibolite layers record the metamorphosed remains of a tholeiitic magma series. The early folding and metamorphism in the Ibadan area was followed by the emplacement of aplite schist and microgranodiorite dikes during the Liberian orogeny 2.75 billion years ago. More intense deformation followed 2.2 billion years ago during the Eburnean orogeny.

Metazquartzites in the Ibadan area, likely from the Proterozoic, are overlain by pelite schist, intruded by mafic sills rich in magnesium. They are overlain by Neoproterozoic pelites,

including phyllite and both muscovite and biotite schists, as well as quartzites that form strike ridges in several parts of Nigeria.

Younger metasediments are found in the southwest and northwest in synclinal schist belts. Compared to the surrounding migmatite-gneiss complexes, these low-grade metamorphic rocks have isoclinal folding and steeply dipping foliation. They have faulted and sheared boundaries with the surrounding rock.

Geologists have interpreted these schist belts the remains of paleo-rift systems. The Pan-African orogeny in the late Proterozoic affected all of the Archean and Paleoproterozoic rocks in the region. Continent-continent collision and eastward subduction affected the southern Trans-Saharan mobile belt and emplaced granitoids throughout the Nigerian Province. In Nigeria, Pan-African orogeny related granite, syenite and diorite intrusions formed between 700 and 500 million years ago and are known as the Older Granites.^[1]

Paleozoic (541-251 million years ago)

In the Cambrian, at the beginning of the Paleozoic, volcanic debris filled molasse grabens, forming dacite and shoshonite, as the Older Granites continued to emplace. In some cases, granite intrusions formed large batholiths and charnockite. The end of the Pan-African orogeny was also accompanied by the intrusion of basalt and dolerite dikes.^[2]

Mesozoic (251-66 million years ago)

In the Mesozoic, during the Jurassic, ring complexes known as the Younger Granites intruded Neoproterozoic and Paleozoic basement rocks in the Jos Plateau, as well as in the Air region in Niger. The Younger Granites are primarily alkali-feldspar granites, although the ring complexes also include rhyolite, gabbro and syenite. The ring dikes tend to be highly mineralized and enriched in niobium and tin.

Large sedimentary basins formed in southern Nigeria, divided by the Okitipupa Ridge. The basins did not begin to fill with sediment until the Albian age of the Cretaceous. In the southeast, poorly bedded sandy shale alternates with layers of sandstone and sandy limestone, containing ammonite, radiolarian, echinoid and gastropod fossils. Subsequently, some of these sedimentary rock layers experienced lead and zinc mineralization.

The arkose sandstone, limestone and shale of the 600 meter thick Odukpani Formation formed during the Cenomanian until the early Turonian, in the vicinity of modern-day Calabar. Fish teeth, ammonites and echinoids date the Eze-Aku Formation to the Turonian, while the blue-gray shales and marl limestone of the Awgu Formation dates to the Coniacian. During the Santonian age of the Cretaceous, sea levels dropped. However, by the Campanian and the Maastrichtian,

the Nkporo Formation records shale, mudstone, limestone and sandstones formed in an offshore environment. In other parts of Nigeria, the Owelli Sandstone, Enugu Shale and Asata Shale formed around the same time in shallow water environments. Other formations of similar age include the ammonite-bearing coals of Mamu Formation and the Nsukka Formation, both from the Maastrichtian.

The Maastrichtian age brought a large marine transgression to southwest Nigeria, depositing the Abeokuta Formation. The Iullemeden Basin, also known as the Sokoto Basin spans Mali, western Niger, northwest Nigeria and northern Benin and began accumulating sediments in the Jurassic, followed by the Maastrichtian Rima Group, which records a brackish environment. Approximately one-tenth of the Chad Basin is situated in Nigeria. Albian Bima sandstone lie unconformably atop Precambrian basement rock, followed by the Turonian limestone and shale sequences of the Gongila Formation. Marine shales of the Fika Formation formed during the Senonian. The Maastrichtian brought a shift to an estuary environment, leading to the deposition of the Gombe Sandstones, which are intercalated with ironstone, siltstone and shales.^[3]

Cenozoic (66 Million Years Ago-Present)

High sea levels continued into the early Cenozoic. In the west, the Akinbo Formation and Ewekoro Formation both deposited in the Paleocene, while the Ino Formation took shape atop the Nsukka in the east, with layers of thick, clay shale. The Sokoto Group in the Iullemeden Basin contains marine sediments. However, by the Eocene, sea levels retreated and afterward Nigeria mainly experienced terrestrial sedimentation.

Around the end of the Cretaceous and the start of the Cenozoic, the sedimentary rocks in the Chad Basin were folded into anticlines and synclines. Erosion created an unconformity with younger rocks. Terrestrial sediments built up in the Paleocene Kerri Kerri Formation, followed by Pliocene lake sediments of the Chad Formation.^[4]

Natural resource geology

Nigeria has extensive natural resources and is the largest crude oil producer in Africa and 20 billion barrels of reserves. As such, petroleum is central to economy of Nigeria, producing 80 percent of government revenues and 95 percent of export earnings. Additionally, Nigeria has 2.6 trillion cubic meters of natural gas and a high overall gas to oil ratio. Seventy percent of both oil and gas resources are onshore.

The country also has extensive mineral deposits, although most are under-exploited. According to the Geological Survey of Nigeria Agency, Nigeria has some 34 known major mineral deposits across the country. Exploration of solid minerals like tin, niobium, lead, zinc and gold, goes back

for more than 90 years, but there has been a world-wide scale production of tin and niobium only.^[6]

Gold mines were active before World War II, extracting from crystalline basement rock in the northwest, but a combination of low gold prices and legal turmoil ended the industry, recently the demand for gold has gone up due its high prices and Gold can be found in commercial quantity in states like Osun, Zamfara and Cross River states in Nigeria. The Younger Granites of the Jos Plateau contain significant tin deposits, mined since before European colonization. However, in recent years, tin mining has been significantly curtailed by flooding in the mines and low tin prices, as well as water pollution from the mines. Tantalite and columbite are both associated with the tin ore in the plateau.

The states of Anambra, Benue, Plateau and Taraba have small-scale lead and zinc mining, from deposits that also have large quantities of cadmium, arsenic and antimony. Barite veins commonly contain lead and zinc in Plateau State and other parts of eastern Nigeria. Kwara State has iron ore in Agbaja Plateau and Itakpe Hills.

Nigeria also has other resources useful for energy and construction, including a poorly understood lignite belt in the south, kaolin, gypsum and feldspar. Coal mining provided much of the country's energy between 1915 and 1960, although the industry has been in a long-running decline, now providing energy only for small-scale kilns and smelters.^[4]

GEOLOGY OF THE STUDY AREAS

Share is underlain by precambian basement complex rocks of Northern Nigeria. Several part of Africa is underlain by crystalline basement complex rocks. The major types of rocks in Share are granite rocks and migmatite. The granite rocks which are member of the older granite suit occupy about 65% of the total area of Share. The first outcrop encountered during the field work exercise was granite, located along Share/Yikpata express way.

Lafiagi is a town in Kwara state, west central Nigeria. On the south bank of the Niger River. It was founded in 1820 by Malam Maliki and his brother Manzums as a fortified town in Nupe territory.

Shonga is a town is Kwara state, with several basement complex and sedimentary terrain. With several conglomeratic sandstones.

CHAPTER THREE

3.1 INSTRUMENTS AND THEIR USES

The mapping was carried out successfully using the essential geological materials as to render effectiveness and accuracy. The materials and functions are tabulated below:

Fig. 4

Fig. 5

Fig. 6

Functions of the field equipment's used during the mapping exercise

EQUIPMENTS	FUNCTION
Clinometers compass	This was used to determine directions, for taking strike and dip on rocks features like foliation.
Hammer / chisel	These were used to break rocks into respective samples for further analysis.
Geographical positioning system (GPS)	This was used in positioning and also to determine direction and location by recording the present point coordinates.
Mapping board	This was used to hold the map for easy work on the map
Digital camera	This was used to take the picture of features seen on the field. Most especially structural features.
Paper tape	This was used to wrap samples for identification and to tape the map on the board

Measuring tape	This was used to take the width of minor outcrops and also the thickness of intrusions or veins.
Marker/colored pencil	The marker was used to label the samples while the colored pencils were used to represent the rock types seen on the field on its right position on the map with the specific color designated for some rocks e.g. red for granitic rocks. See figure 1.1.
Topographic map of the area	This revealed the geographical and topographical information concerning the mapped area.
Field note	This was used to record information observed on the field with some sketches to complement the recorded information
Field boot and wears	These were worn for protection on the field particular in the bush.
Tracing paper	This is a transparent paper upon which the geologic map is been produced by representation of geological rock units and features found in the process of mapping.
Sample bag	This is a strong, light weighted bag used to convey the samples from the field to the base.

CHAPTER FOUR

FIELD WORK IN DETAIL

DATE: 11TH MAY, 2023.

DAY: 1

ARRIVAL.....

DATE: 12TH MAY, 2023.

DAY: 2

SHARE

LOCATION: 1

LONGITUDE: 8°48'22" N

LATITUDE: 4°57'44" E

ELEVATION: 315m

DESCRIPTION OF LOCATION: Western side of Share oke ode, about 100m+ from the road,

DESCRIPTION OF THE OUTCROP: High rising

TEXTURE: coarse (phaneritic)

STRUCTURE: fault, quartz vein

ROCK TYPE: Both Sedimentary and Metamorphic Rock

ROCK NAME: Conglomeratic sandstone

COLOUR: Reddish brown

MODE OF TRANSPORTATION: Alluvial setting

MECHANISM OF TRANSPORTATION: Bottom traction

Share is a part of Bida Basin. The basin is divided stratigraphy into North and South.

The Northern part contain formations like Bida formation, Sakpe formation, Enagi formation and the Batati formation. The Southern part is the Lokoja formation, Patti formation and the Agbaja formation.

The Nigerian basement is divided into Migmatite gneiss (Banded gneiss and Biotite gneiss), Schist belt (Older and Younger metasediment) and Pan African granitoids (Older and Younger granite).

The outcrop is a nonconformity showing highly weathered basement complex overlaid by sedimentary rocks with an erosional surfaces consisting of conglomerate forming Disconformity. The exposure of the outcrop is due to the mining process. The nonconformity is as a result of leaching and lateritic soil. It's has a penetration of Quartz vein and iron material such as bauxite, aluminum oxide.

Fig. 7: A nonconformity outcrop

DATE: 12TH MAY, 2023.

DAY: 2

SHARE

LOCATION: 2

LONGITUDE: 8°48'329" N

LATITUDE: 4°57'806" E

ELEVATION: 304m

DESCRIPTION OF LOCATION: Eastern Share oke ode road, 80m from the road.

DESCRIPTION OF OUTCROP: Low lying

TEXTURE: Porphyritic

STRUCTURE: Folds, Quartzvein intrusion, Pegmatitic fold intrusion, Joint and Diorite intrusion.

MINERALOGY: Quartz, Feldspar, Mica and Biotite.

ROCK TYPE: Metamorphic Rock

ROCK NAME: Migmatite

Igneous rock are Granite, and Diorite

Metamorphic rock are Biotite, Gneiss, and Amphibolite.

Fig. 8: Migmatite

DATE: 12TH MAY, 2023.

DAY: 2

SHARE

LOCATION: 3

LONGITUDE: 8°47'0" N

LATITUDE: 4°57'54" E

ELEVATION: 280m

DESCRIPTION OF LOCATION: 70m from the Western Share Oke Ode road, 500m away from the police headquarters.

DESCRIPTION OF THE OUTCROP: Low lying, vegetative environment

TEXTURE: Fine grained (Aphanitic)

STRUCTURE: Quartz vein, Pegmatite vein, fracture, Quartzofeldspatic intrusion

MINERALOGY: Quartz, feldspar biotite

COLOUR: Malanocratic (Dark)

ROCK TYPE: Igneous Rock

ROCK NAME: Diorite

Measurements taken for the structures are:

Strike of fracture: 288°

Strike of Quartz: 222° (width = 2mm)

Strike of Quartzofeldspatic: 228°

Fig. 9: Diorite

DATE: 12TH MAY, 2023.

DAY: 2

SHARE

LOCATION: 4

LONGITUDE: 8°47'0" N

LATITUDE: 4°57'59" E

ELEVATION: 280m

DESCRIPTION OF LOCATION: 200m away from the Share Oke ode road, South East

DESCRIPTION OF OUTCROP: Gentle rising

TEXTURE: Coarse (Phaneritic)

STRUCTURES: Fold, Quartz vein, Pegmatitic vein, Quartzofeldspatic vein, Fracture, Xenolith

MINEROLOGY: Quartz, Feldspar, Biotite

COLOUR: Leucocratic (Light colored)

ROCK TYPE: Igneous Rock

ROCK NAME: Granite (intrudes by Diorite)

The outcrop is a granite intruded by a diorite. A sharp share zone occur between the Diorite and Granite. The Diorite is finer than the granite.

There occur a dextrite fault on the granite.

There is a presence of an inclusion called Xenolith on the outcrop.

Measurements taken from the structures are :

Strike of Pegmatite : 348°, 294°, 318°

Strike of Quartz : 284°, 272° (width = 1mm), 228° (width = 4mm)

Fig. 10: Granite

Fig. 11: Granite with Xenolith inclusion

DATE: 12TH MAY, 2023.

DAY: 2

SHARE

LOCATION: 5

LONGITUDE: 8°47'42" N

LATITUDE: 4°57'59" E

ELEVATION: 290m

Description of location : opposite the holy order of Cherubim and Seraphim Movement Church Olorun Ishadi, Ifelodun LGA Share.

NOTE: LOCATION 5 HAS THE SAME CHARACTERISTICS AND FEATURES WITH LOCATION 4.

Fig. 12: Granite

DATE: 12TH MAY, 2023.

DAY: 2

SHARE

LOCATION: 6

LONGITUDE: 8°48'54" N

LATITUDE: 4°58'37" E

ELEVATION: 280m

DESCRIPTION OF LOCATION: South Western side of Share General Hospital, 250m away from the road

DESCRIPTION OF OUTCROP: Gentle rising

TEXTURE: Coarse grained

STRUCTURES: Quartzofeldspathic fold, Quartz vein, Sinistral fault

MINEROLOGY: Quartz, Feldspar, Mica

ROCK TYPE: Metamorphic Rock

ROCK NAME: Granite gneiss

COLOUR: Mesocratic (Intermediate)

Fig. 13: Granite gneiss

Fig. 14: Quartzofeldspathic fold

DATE: 13TH MAY, 2023.

DAY: 3

SHONGA

LOCATION: 7

LONGITUDE: 9°1'28" N

LATITUDE: 5°8'48" E

ELEVATION: 100m

DESCRIPTION OF LOCATION: Shonga, located at the other side of the river that flows from the River Niger.

DESCRIPTION OF OUTCROP: High rising

STRUCTURE: ripple marks, cross bedding, planar bedding, parallel bedding, bioturbation

ROCK TYPE: Sedimentary Rock

ROCK NAME: Conglomeratic Sandstone

These outcrop is located at the Northern part of the Bida basin, Enagi formation to be precise. The characteristic of Enagi formation are : Sandstone, Claystone and Conglomerates. Logging was carried out at this outcrop. Several structures including burrows were found. The burrows are made by some organisms and may also shows indications of marine flow. The thickest portions of the basin accommodate about 3000m conglomerates, sandstones and claystone.

The sandstone is the reservoir holding the water capacity although the water are not of good quality due to the presence of the clay.

Method of Sedimentary Rock Logging

You log from the thickest section

Vertical scale is the thickness

Horizontal scale is the grain size

Take each bed after the other and you identify each bed by looking at the physical characteristics such as colour, texture, structure, geometry etc

DATE: 13TH MAY, 2023.

DAY: 3

SHONGA

LOCATION: 8

LONGITUDE: 9°2'20" N

LATITUDE: 5°9'19" E

ELEVATION: 70m.

DESCRIPTION OF LOCATION: located at the right of the location 7 outcrop.

Location 8 is a river that flows from the River Niger.

The hydrologic cycle involves the continuous circulation of water in the Earth-Atmosphere system. At its core, the water cycle is the motion of the water from the ground to the atmosphere and back again. Of the many processes involved in the hydrologic cycle, the most important are...

- evaporation
- transpiration
- condensation
- precipitation
- runoff

It is a surface water because it is exposed to the surface and flows freely. It's belong to atmospheric water because it's comes from precipitation. It is a Non renewable water.

Fig.18 & 19: Shows the river the flows from the River Niger

DATE: 14TH MAY, 2023.

DAY: 4

LAFIAGI

LOCATION: 9

LONGITUDE: 8°50'10" N

LATITUDE: 5°04'20" E

ELEVATION: 170m.

DESCRIPTION OF LOCATION: Kokuna village along Share-Lafiagi road.

DESCRIPTION OF OUTCROP: Low Lying.

STRUCTURE: Cross parallel stratification, laminations

ROCK TYPE: Sedimentary Rock

ROCK NAME: Sandstone

The sediment in this location are transported by river. They are siliciclastic sediment exposed to the surface by a nearby river channel.

The laminations are formed as the sediment are being transported by water, the water sediment are deposited under the influence of gravity.

Factors that influence the deposition of water sediment under the influence of gravity are: (1) Buoyancy density between the particle and molecules between water. (2) Fluctuation of water medium.

The outcrop contain conglomerates which are micaceous in content. The sediment pattern is fining upward to coarsening upward.

Pebbles mesometric can be done by measuring the long axis, intermediate axis and short axis.

Transportation occur at the upper part of the river and Deposition at the lower part of the river.

Fossils are preserved in fine sediment than the coarse sediment because they contain pore spaces.

Fig. 20: Sandstone

DATE: 14TH MAY, 2023.

DAY: 4

LAFIAGI

LOCATION: 10

LONGITUDE: 8°48'53" N

LATITUDE: 5°05'04" E

ELEVATION: 150m

DESCRIPTION OF LOCATION: Road cut exposure along Lafiagi road.

DESCRIPTION OF OUTCROP: Low Lying.

ROCK TYPE: Metamorphic Rock

ROCK NAME: Mica schist

Measurement taken on the outcrop

Strike and Dip: 184°, 22°W

208°, 10°W

358°, 50°W

350°, 28°W

354°, 44°W

Schist metamorphosed from shale. Materials that are micaceous mainly muscovite are present in the outcrop.

Fig. 21: Mica Schist

DATE: 14TH MAY, 2023.

DAY: 4

LAFIAGI

LOCATION: 11

LONGITUDE: 8°49'40" N

LATITUDE: 5°05'50" E

ELEVATION: 130m

DESCRIPTION OF LOCATION: Lafiagi road

DESCRIPTION OF OUTCROP: Low Lying

ROCK TYPE: Metamorphic Rock

ROCK NAME: Schist

The schist is in the NS direction. Their is presence of Muscovite, Biotite and Mica schist.

Types of schist are Biotite schist, Stereolite schist, Muscovite schist and Mica schist.

The outcrop is a part of metasedimentary rock schist. Schist belt within the precambriam contain gold, silver etc

The schist at the location are deepen. And contain meandering nature of river, Fluvial deposition of sediment.

A quartz vein fault was discovered on a prophyritic granite with an amphibolite cross cutting the quartz vein intruding the prophyritic granite.

The fault is coming toward the Western direction. The fault is a sinistral fault.

Schist metamorphose to Schistocity which is an indication of cleavage.

Basically the schist have Mica schist, Schistocity cleavage and it is a foliated medium grained metamorphic rock with a deep surface.

Strike and Dip : 318°NW , 50°E

316°NW , 60°E

Fig. 22: Schist

Fig. 23: Sinistral fault

DATE: 14TH MAY, 2023.

DAY: 4

LAFIAGI

LOCATION: 12

LONGITUDE: 8°46'22" N

LATITUDE: 5°12'11" E

ELEVATION: 270m

DESCRIPTION OF LOCATION: Gedeworo along Share-Lafiagi road.

DESCRIPTION OF OUTCROP: High rising.

ROCK TYPE: Sedimentary Rock

ROCK NAME: Conglomeratic sandstone.

The outcrop is a road cut exposure of clastic sediment. Logging was carried out at this location. It's a sandstone containing lots of conglomerates that is why it is known as conglomeratic sandstone. The Pebbles are imbricated, and are relics of quartzite. The exposure is a part of Bida formation which is the oldest formation in the Bida basin.

Fig. 24: Conglomeratic Sandstone

Fig. 25: Logging book

DATE: 14TH MAY, 2023.

DAY: 4

LAFIAGI

LOCATION: 13

LONGITUDE: 8°48'48" N

LATITUDE: 5°14'05" E

ELEVATION: 270m

DESCRIPTION OF LOCATION: Maganiko village along Lafiagi road, it is a road cut exposure.

DESCRIPTION OF OUTCROP: Gentle rising

TEXTURE: coarse grained

STRUCTURE: Bioturbation, burrows

ROCK TYPE: Sedimentary Rock

ROCK NAME: Conglomeratic sandstone

We have sandstone and conglomeratic sandstone.

The sandstone are massive and of different shape such as rounded, angular etc.

At the outcrop we have presence of Bioturbation, trace fossils (burrows) which are preserved laterally or vertically. The conglomerates are grain supported. The outcrop has a cyclic sedimentation that are of fining upward sequence.

Fig. 26: Conglomeratic Sandstone

DATE: 14TH MAY, 2023.

DAY: 4

LAFIAGI

LOCATION: 14

LONGITUDE: 8°50'57" N

LATITUDE: 5°24'58" E

ELEVATION: 120m

DESCRIPTION OF LOCATION: Lafiagi road.

DESCRIPTION OF OUTCROP: High rising.

STRUCTURE: Bioturbation, burrows, ripple marks, cross lamination, parallel lamination.

ROCK TYPE: Sedimentary Rock

ROCK NAME: Conglomeratic Sandstone

From field studies, group work analysis and lectures received, it is evident that the area studied shows that the Share Granite belt is predominantly made up of basement rock and sedimentary rock. Other geologic features include inclusions and structural features such as ripple mark, cross bedding, fractures and micro folds were seen. Only a few stream channels were encountered, some are seasonal. Hospitals and market were seen.

Conclusively, the results of this field exercise shows that the study area is made up the Basement complex and also sedimentary rock, the Granite and various lithologic units comprising of Conglomeratic sandstone, Conglomerate and Buried Conglomerate.

REFERENCES:

1. ^ Schlüter, Thomas (2008). *Geological Atlas of Africa*. Springer. pp. 196–197.
2. ^ Schlüter 2008 p. 196.
3. ^ Schlüter 2008, pp. 197–198.
4. ^ a b Schlüter 2008 p. 198.
5. ^ Obaje, Nuhu George (2009). *Geology and Mineral Resources of Nigeria*. Springer. p. 117.